

Mixed ligand peroxovanadium complexes containing L-carnosine

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Manuscript received 1 October 2007, accepted 21 November 2007

Abstract : Mixed ligand peroxy complexes containing L-carnosine, either in its neutral or deprotonated form have been synthesized and characterized. The complexes have been formulated as $K[VO(O_2)L].H_2O$ (1), $K[VO(O_2)_2(H_2L)].H_2O$ (2), $[V_2O_2(O_2)_3(H_2L)_3].H_2O$ (3), where $H_2L = L$ -carnosine. The ligand in its dideprotonated form in the complex (1), acts as a tridentate ligand, coordinating to vanadium through three donor atoms namely the oxygen atom of the carboxylate group, two nitrogen one each from the primary amine and the other from the amide group of the ligand. The ligand in acidic pH, behaves as a zwitterions, acts as bidentate through both oxygen of the carboxylate group in the complex (2) and as monodentate through oxygen of the carboxylate group in the complex (3). The peroxide ligand in all the complexes are chelated to vanadium and in the triperoxy complex, additionally it also bridge two vanadium atoms.

Keywords : Peroxovanadium, L-carnosine, synthesis.

Introduction

L-Carnosine is a very important peptide, namely in its ability to act as a ligand in the generation of coordination complexes with different metallic cations. In its interactions with metal ions, carnosine acts a polydentate ligand offering six potential binding sites, the two imidazole nitrogen, one carboxylate and one amino group, and the peptide linkage¹. The type of complexes formed strongly depends on the metal cation, the ligand to metal ratios, and the pH of the solution².

L-Carnosine (H_2L)

In the pH range between 6.0 to 8.5, the interaction of the oxovanadium(IV) with the imidazole group of four different ligands molecules was confirmed, indicating the presence of an axially coordinated water molecule in the complex $[VO(Car)_4(H_2O)]^{2,3}$. ESR spectra also suggest some weak interactions through carboxylate groups at pH 2.5–3.0⁴. Recently, it has been shown that whereas α -alanyl-L-histidine interacts strongly with vanadates(V),

generating very stable complexes⁵ which may be useful as models for the vanadate-peptide interactions. But carnosine does not interact with these VO_3^- and other oxovanadium(V) anions.

There has been a continuous upsurge in interest in the chemistry of vanadium peroxides mainly owing to their insulin-mimetic properties^{6,7}, their ability to oxidize organic and inorganic substrates⁸ as well as their potential as models for the understanding vanadium dependent biogenic systems⁶. The majority of known synthetic hetero-ligand peroxovanadate(V) complexes represent anionic mono, di or tetra oxo complexes containing the peroxy group bonded to vanadium in a side-on fashion⁷. Reports related to dinuclear peroxovanadium(V) compounds with a bridging peroxy group are limited⁹ and it is an area needing exploration. The synthesis of new members of peroxy bridged compounds of the type $[V_2O_2(O_2)_3(\text{di-peptide})_3].H_2O$ and $[V_2O_2(O_2)_3(\text{tri-peptide})_2].H_2O$ have been reported^{10,11}. These triperoxy divanadate complexes distinguished themselves in terms of their spectral as well as solution properties from the known peroxovanadium complexes possessing exclusively terminally bound peroxy groups.

Thus the paucity of information on peroxy bridged divanadates and the current intensive search for bio-relevant vanadium complexes^{6,8,12} prompted us to direct our efforts in establishing viable synthetic routes to new dimeric peroxy vanadates in a biogenic ligand environ-

ment. Hence, the dimeric mixed ligand vanadium peroxo complexes with peptides can act as a model compound towards vanadate dependent haloperoxidase. L-Carnosine is a dipeptide, can serve as a multidentate ligand and very little studies have been made on its vanadium(V) complexes. Hence, attempts have been made to synthesise mixed ligand peroxo complexes of vanadium(V) with L-carnosine.

Experimental

Vanadium pentoxide and L-carnosine were from Sigma Chemical Company, USA; the other chemicals used were analytical grade.

A Perkin-Elmer series II, CHNS Analyser, model 2400 at the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Kolkata, was used for C, H, N microanalyses. Vanadium was estimated by titration with a Fe^{2+} solution in the presence of sulphonated diphenylamine as indicator, after decomposing the sample with sodium peroxide¹³.

The UV-Vis spectra were recorded in aqueous solution using Shimadzu 2401 PC, and the IR spectra in KBr pellets with Perkin-Elmer L120-00A FT-IR spectrometer. The NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker ACP-300 spectrometer operating at 75 MHz. DSS [sodium-3-(trimethylsilyl)-1-propane sulfonate] was used as an external reference.

Syntheses :

Ligand : L-Carnosine (β -alanyl-L-histidine) is used. L-Carnosine is a polydentate ligand offering six potential binding sites, the two imidazole N-, one carboxylate O-, and one amino group N- and the peptide linkage, N-, O-. It can exist as zwitterion (H_2L) or as dideprotonated form (L) as shown below :

(L)

L-Carnosine as zwitterion (H_2L)

Complex : $\text{K}[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)\text{L}]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1) : A quantity of 0.91 g (5.0 mmol) of V_2O_5 was dissolved in 0.65 g (11.6 mmol) of KOH in 10 ml of water. To this was added 1.17 g L-carnosine (5.17 mmol) in 20 ml of aqueous methanol

(L')

Dideprotonated form (L)

containing 0.2 g NaOH (5.00 mmol). A clear yellow solution was obtained, pH controlled at 7.5 by adding 0.1 M KOH solution. It was cooled to 5 °C and to it pre-cooled 30% H_2O_2 (0.28 ml, 2.5 mmol) was added dropwise with continuous stirring for 30 min. The color of the solution became yellowish red. The orange crystals were isolated by adding ethanol to the mixture. Yield : 1.10 g, 58% (Found : V, 13.91; C, 28.12; H, 3.54; N, 14.42. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_7\text{VK}$ (formula weight : 380.2) : V, 13.40; C, 28.41; H, 3.71; N, 14.74%).

$\text{K}[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2) : 0.91 g (5 mmol) of V_2O_5 was dissolved in 0.65 g (11.6 mmol) of KOH in 10 ml of water. To this 1.17 g L-carnosine (5.17 mmol) in 20 ml aqueous methanol containing 0.2 g NaOH (5.00 mmol). To the clear yellow solution obtained, 0.1 M KOH was added dropwise to make pH 5.5. After stirring the solution, it was cooled at 5 °C and pre-cooled 30% H_2O_2 (0.28 ml, 2.5 mmol) was added to it dropwise with continuous stirring for 30 min. Yellow crystals were separated by adding ethanol. Yield : 0.92 g, 48% (Found : V, 13.16; C, 28.12; H, 3.54; N, 14.42. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_7\text{VK}$ (formula weight : 382.2) : V, 13.33; C, 28.26; H, 4.22; N, 14.66%).

$[\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2)_3(\text{H}_2\text{L})_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3) : 0.91 g (5 mmol) of V_2O_5 was dissolved in 10 ml H_2O . Then 1.17 g L-carnosine (5.17 mmol) in 20 ml aqueous methanol containing 0.2 g NaOH (5.00 mmol) was added. A clear yellow solution of pH 3 was obtained. After stirring the solution, it was cooled to 5 °C and pre-cooled 30% H_2O_2 (0.28 ml, 2.5 mmol) was added dropwise with continuous stirring for 30 min. The yellowish red crystals are separated by adding ethanol to the mixture. Yield : 1.99 g, 43% (Found : V, 11.57; C, 35.12; H, 4.16; N, 17.96. Calcd. values for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_{18}\text{V}_2$ (formula weight : 926.3) : V, 11.0; C, 34.98; H, 4.79; N, 18.14%).

Results and discussion

Solubility : The complexes are stable in air but in

Table 1. IR spectra of L-carnosine and complexes

L-Carnosine	K[VO(O ₂)L].H ₂ O (1)	K[VO(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ L)].H ₂ O (2)	[V ₂ O ₂ (O ₂) ₃ (H ₂ L) ₃].H ₂ O (3)	Assignment
3240 s, br	3312 s, br	3280 s, br	3275 s, br	$\nu(\text{NH}_2)$, $\nu(\text{OH})$
1655 s	1625 vs	1656 vs	1662 vs	$\nu(\text{NHCO})$
1585 s	1555 s	1621 s	1617 s	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$
1410 s	1386 s	1386 s	1378 s	$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$
1270 m	1258 m	-	-	$\rho(\text{NH}_2)$
1160 m	1115 m	1157 s	1155 s	$\nu(\text{CN})/\rho(\text{N}^+\text{H}_3)$
	-	1072 m	1068 m	$\rho(\text{N}^+\text{H}_3)$
	973 vs	947 vs	935 vs	$\nu(\text{VO})$
	896 s	872 s	878 s, 814 m	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{M-O}_2)$
	618 s	638 m	630 m	
	575 m	-	-	$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{V-N})$
	558 m	545 m	560 m	$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{M-O}_2)$

solution decomposes very slowly. All the complexes are readily soluble in water, moderately soluble in DMF, DMSO and insoluble in common alcohols.

IR spectroscopy : The important bands of the ligands and the complexes and their assignments have been presented in Table 1. The IR absorption spectra of the complexes exhibit a similar pattern. The complex (1) shows a strong absorption band around 3300 cm^{-1} , assigned to the overlap of the NH and OH stretching frequencies. The amide carbonyl frequency appeared at 1625 cm^{-1} , a shift to around 30 cm^{-1} compared to that of free L-carnosine (1655 cm^{-1}). This lowering of the amide frequency may be due to the deprotonation of the amide carbonyl group of L-carnosine¹⁴ and simultaneous coordination to vanadium through amide-N atom. The two strong absorption peaks in the complexes around 1555 cm^{-1} and 1386 cm^{-1} are due to asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxylate groups which shifts to 30 cm^{-1} , compared to free carnosine indicating coordination through the oxygen of the carboxylate groups. The medium intensity band in the low frequency range at 570 cm^{-1} , may be assigned to vanadium nitrogen stretching frequency only present in complex (1).

The presence of two bands at 1072 cm^{-1} and 1068 cm^{-1} in complex (2) and complex (3) respectively, indicate that amino acid is present as zwitterions. The asymmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxylate groups at 1621 cm^{-1} and 1617 cm^{-1} for complex (2) and (3) respectively, indicate coordination of the carboxylate in bidentate manner. The bands around 875 cm^{-1} for the peroxy groups confirm its attachment in bidentate manner. Peroxy group also acts as bridge between two vanadium atoms.

Thus, IR spectral data suggests that the dideprotonated L-carnosine coordinates to vanadium in the complex (1) by three donor atoms namely, the oxygen of the carboxylate group and two nitrogen, one each from primary amine and other from the deprotonated amide group. In complex (2), L-carnosine is in zwitterions form and act as a bidentate ligand coordinating to vanadium through the two carboxylate oxygens. In complex (3) L-carnosine also is in zwitterion form, one ligand attached to vanadium as monodentate through oxygen of carboxylate oxygen. The two peroxide O_2^{2-} , one as chelate and another as a bridge between two vanadium atoms. The very strong band around 970 cm^{-1} may be assigned due to the $\text{V}=\text{O}$ stretching vibration, indicating that the VO core remains intact. Shifting of lower frequency about 35 cm^{-1} in complex (2) and (3) is probably due to bridging oxygen with vanadium atom.

Behaviour in solution : K[VO(O₂)L].H₂O complex (1) is stable in aqueous solution. Evolution of gases was not observed immediately. Weak broad charge transfer band at 328 nm was observed due to transition from the π -electrons of the ligand system to the vacant d-orbital of the vanadium center. The solution of complex (1) deepens gradually and the compound transformed to K[VO₂L].2H₂O having λ_{max} at 230 nm and the compound was isolated and characterised as published earlier¹⁵. The measured pH of the solution is 7.0. The 230 nm band is due to a charge transfer transition from the ligand to the metal. A tautomeric change from the N(3)-H to N(1)-H takes place in the imidazole moiety of L-carnosine as established from ¹³C NMR spectrum of the complex (Table 2).

The ¹³C NMR spectrum of the complex K[VO₂L].2H₂O¹⁶ was recorded in the solid state to avoid

Table 2. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of L-carnosine and isolated compound

Compd.	CO_2^-	NHCO	C(2)	C(5)	C(4)	$\text{C}_{\alpha'}$	$\text{C}_{\beta'}$	C_{α}	C_{β}
L-Carnosine	178.6	169.5	136.2	136.2	115.8	56.9	37.9	34.0	32.4
$\text{K}[\text{VO}_2\text{L}]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	176.9	172.4	149.2	135.7	127.9	57.4	38.6	38.6	32.4

ligand exchange of the complex in solution, particularly that of the imidazole moiety in the L-carnosine molecule which undergo tautomeric change. The C(2) and C(5) signals are overlapped at 136.2 ppm in the free ligand, but in the complex the signals are shifted downfield and are now separated by 13.5 ppm. The resonance signal at 115.8 ppm due to C(4) in the ligand appeared 127.9 ppm in the complex, downfield shift of the C(2) and C(4) signals indicate a drastic change within the ligand, especially involving the imidazole moiety. The imidazole ring in L-carnosine exists predominantly as the N(3)-H tautomer which excludes the possibility of a N(1)-H tautomer. The ratio of the N(3)-H and N(1)-H tautomer form of the imidazole moiety in L-carnosine has been reported¹⁷ to be 2 : 1.

$\text{K}[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex (2) is also soluble in water and stable in aqueous solution at least for 12 h. No immediate release of bubbles from the aqueous solution has been observed. But, $[\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2)_3(\text{H}_2\text{L})_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex (3) is unstable in aqueous solution with immediate release of oxygen.

Conclusion :

From the above discussion we can conclude that at different pH values i.e. pH = 7, 5.5 and 3, three different peroxovanadium complexes $[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)\text{L}]^-$, $[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})]^-$, $[\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2)_3(\text{H}_2\text{L})_3]$ are formed with the reaction of vanadium pentoxide, hydrogen peroxide and L-carnosine. The coordination modes of the dipeptide L-carnosine also change i.e. its zwitterions form and dideprotonated form, depending on the pH value. L-Carnosine can act either as monodentate ligand and or bidentate or as a tridentate ligand. In the complex (3) peroxide group acts as monodentate ligand which bridged two vanadium atoms. The proposed structures have been presented as :

Proposed structure of $[\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2)_3(\text{H}_2\text{L})_3]$

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their grateful thanks to DST, Government of India for providing facilities to record UV-visible and FT-IR spectra under FIST Program. One of the author (A. Chakrabarty) thanks UGC, New Delhi for sanctioning one minor project (sanction no. PSW081/05-06).

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